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Acute cholecystitis in elderly and high-risk surgical patients: is percutaneous cholecystostomy preferable to emergency cholecystectomy?

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The Ethical Committee of the Hospital Clínico University of Valencia has approved the study.

Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To investigate whether percutaneous cholecystostomy (PC) for the treatment of acute calculous cholecystitis (ACC) has better results than emergency cholecystectomy (EC) in elderly and high-risk surgical patients.

METHODS: Patients ≥ 70 years and/or \geq ASA-PS 3 with ACC treated with PC or EC between 2005 and 2016 were retrospectively reviewed. Both techniques were compared regarding morbi-mortality, hospital stay, complications and readmissions. A subgroup analysis in higher risk patients (≥ 70 years plus \geq ASA-PS 3) was also performed. A binary logistic regression analysis for outcome variables to calculate the OR was carried out.

RESULTS: 461 patients were included in the study. The results of PC were worse compared to EC: 30-days mortality (8.6% vs. 1.7%, OR 18.4), 90-days mortality (10.4% vs. 2.1%, OR 10.3), length of stay (days) (13.21 ± 8.2 vs. 7.48 ± 7.67 , OR 8.7) and readmission rate (35.1% vs. 12.6%, OR 4.7). Complications were lower for PC (14% vs. 22.6%, OR 0.41), but there were no significant differences in the number of severe complications (Clavien-Dindo \geq III). Higher-risk subgroup analysis ($n=193$; PC=128, EC=65) showed similar results to the whole series. Patients with ACC for more than 3 days had more risk of severe complications in both groups (OR 2.26; OR 2.76).

CONCLUSION: PC was associated with an increased risk of mortality at 30 and 90 days, more readmissions and longer hospital stay. Although PC presents a lower risk of complications, the percentage of severe complications (Clavien-Dindo \geq III) does not show significant differences.

INTRODUCTION

Acute cholecystitis is one of the most frequent pathologies in daily clinical practice in surgery. It represents one-third of the surgical emergency hospital admissions and is the cause of abdominal pain in 3-10% of patients who come to the emergency room^[1,2]. The treatment of choice for acute calculous cholecystitis (ACC) in patients fit for surgery is laparoscopic cholecystectomy^[3,4]. However, in elderly patients or high surgical risk patients due to associated comorbidities, percutaneous cholecystostomy (PC) represents a less invasive procedure, which could be indicated as an alternative to surgery^[5,6].

There is a lack of consensus regarding which patients should be considered as high surgical risk, which scales should be used to assess the risk and whether age should be a factor to be taken into account. Therefore, the indications and contraindications of each technique do not have well-established limits and the choice between one or the other depends on the expertise of the surgeon who treats the patient.

In recent years, the use of PC has gradually increased as an alternative treatment for ACC^[7,8] probably due to the fact that it is easy and less invasive. However, the technique is not a definitive treatment for ACC in most cases and there is scarce evidence to support this management.

The aim of this study is to compare the results of treating patients with ACC in a large cohort of elderly and high-risk surgical patients by means of emergency cholecystectomy (EC) versus PC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design of the study and inclusion criteria

A retrospective cohort study was carried out with patients suffering from ACC treated at our tertiary center between January 2005 and December 2016, and with the following inclusion criteria: 1) patients aged 70 years or older, 2) ASA-PS (American Society of Anaesthesiologists physical status) classification system^[9] ≥ 3 ; 3) treatment by either emergency cholecystectomy (EC) or PC and 4) follow-up of at least 18 months.

A database with the information of the patients was elaborated. The variables analyzed were epidemiological dates, comorbidities, time of evolution, hospital stay in days, treatment (PC or EC), complications and mortality at 30 and 90 days after treatment.

A first analysis of the data was performed with all patients who met the criteria for inclusion in the study. Subsequently, the same analysis of the data was performed with the subgroup of patients considered high-risk (≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3).

Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the hospital approved the study.

Techniques and indications

PC was performed by the hospital's interventional radiology department. The technique was carried out under local anaesthesia using ultrasound control and transhepatic puncture, leaving a 7-French pigtail catheter lodged inside the gallbladder^[10,11]. EC was performed by the surgeons on call at the hospital. All surgeries began with a laparoscopic approach in French position. If a laparoscopic procedure could not be completed, a right subcostal incision was made. **During the**

surgical procedure the cystic duct and the cystic artery were identified before sectioning following the technique of critical view of safety described by Strasberg et al ^[12,13,14].

The choice of the technique (PC or EC) was decided at the discretion of the surgeon responsible for each case after evaluation of the general physical condition of the patient, age and the availability of the operating room.

Definitions

Classification of surgical risk: ASA-PS classification scale was used. High-risk patient was defined as ASA-PS ≥ 3 , which represents a patient with a severe systemic disease^[9].

Comorbidities: In addition to ASA-PS, comorbidities were evaluated by the Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI)^[15]. High-risk patient was defined as CCI ≥ 6 according with the Tokyo guidelines for the management of ACC^[4]. Diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension and heart disease were also analyzed separately because they are the most prevalent comorbidities in our study group.

Time of evolution: time in days from the appearance of the first symptoms until the patient was admitted to the hospital.

Complications: in-hospital complications were categorized according to the Dindo-Clavien classification^[16].

Hospital stay: time in days between admission and discharge.

Readmission: this condition was defined as admission to the hospital within 30 days after being discharged from the previous episode. A further classification defined whether the cause was due to biliary pathology, technical complication or others.

Mortality: 30 and 90 days mortality referred to patients who underwent PC or EC and died during hospitalization or after discharge within 30 or 90 days after the procedure.

Statistical analysis

The IBM SPSS Statistics® software version 24.0 for Windows® was used for the statistical analysis. A descriptive analysis of quantitative variables, measures of central tendency and dispersion (mean and standard deviation), was carried out. In addition, a statistical inference analysis was performed to detect significant associations. Finally, we made a binary logistic regression analysis for the outcome variables to calculate the odds ratio (OR) taking into account as confounding variables (age, sex, comorbidities, ASA-PS and time of evolution of the ACC). For the mortality variables at 30 and 90 days the following confounding variables were added: complications, hospital stay and readmissions. Statistical significance was considered for a value of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

From January 2005 to December 2016, a total of 461 patients with the diagnosis of ACC who met the criteria for inclusion in the study were admitted at our department. 222 (48.2%) were treated with PC and 239 (51.8%) underwent EC. Figure 1 shows the distribution of patients according to the criteria for inclusion in the study.

The demographic profile, time of evolution, comorbidities and the results comparing PC and EC of the global sample of patients are shown in Table 1. The results of the 193 patients included in the subgroup of patients with the highest risk (patients ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3) can be seen in Table 2.

In both groups there were differences in age, greater in patients who had undergone PC, and gender. In the whole series the evolution time of ACC was longer

in patients undergoing PC. However, this difference disappeared in the subgroup of patients ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3 . **There were no differences in the CCI either in the whole series nor in the high-risk subgroup.** Although there were more patients with diabetes mellitus and heart disease in the surgery group, this difference disappeared in the subgroup of high-risk patients.

Complications occurring during the 30 days after the first day of admission, regardless of whether they were directly related to the technique (PC or EC) or not, were collected. In all cases, complications were more frequent in the EC group but around 80% of the complications were Clavien-Dindo I-II. No significant differences were found in the severe complications (Clavien-Dindo \geq III) between both techniques in the study groups. Hospital stay and readmissions were statistically favorable for the group of patients who underwent surgery.

Of the 222 patients undergoing PC, 40 (18%) were **operated upon** in a second admission at the hospital. 37 of the 40 patients (92.5%) **underwent cholecystectomy** by laparoscopic approach and 10 (25%) presented some type of complication. Mean hospital stay in patients undergoing cholecystectomy after PC was 4.78 ± 4.91 days. Mortality at 30 and 90 days was lower for operated patients from the two groups of the study. However, in the group of patients ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3 this mortality rate did not reach statistical significance.

Table 4 shows the results of the binary logistic regression analysis for the two study groups. The outcome variables were: **intervention**, complications, severe complications, hospital stay (≤ 7 days versus > 7 days), readmissions and mortality at 30 and 90 days.

Patients undergoing PC had a lower risk of complications in general. There was a greater risk of severe complications in both groups in patients suffering for three days or more with ACC. In addition, ASA-PS ≥ 3 was associated with an increased risk of any type of complications.

The risk of hospital stay ≥ 7 days was clearly higher in patients who underwent a PC (OR 8.708, $p < 0.001$). The prolongation of hospital stay was influenced by age ≥ 70 years, ASA-PS ≥ 3 , time of evolution of acute process and appearance of complications.

The patients treated with PC had a higher readmission risk compared to the operated patients, especially in the subgroup of high-risk patients (OR 4.685, $p < 0.001$, OR 8.935, $p < 0.001$).

Finally, there was a greater risk of mortality at 30 and 90 days in both groups for patients who were treated with PC as can be seen in Table 3.

DISCUSSION

The gold standard treatment for ACC is surgery. Current recommendations indicate laparoscopic cholecystectomy in all three-severity levels of gallbladder inflammation (mild, moderate or severe) providing the patient can tolerate surgery after evaluating the surgical risk^[4]. The severity of the symptomatology and the life-threatening potential are determined, in part, by the patient's underlying diseases. The problem is that there is no consensus when evaluating the surgical risk. The WSES (World Society of Emergency Surgery) 2016 clinical guidelines consider that patient age above 80 in acute cholecystitis is a risk factor for worse clinical evolution, morbidity and mortality^[3]. Several studies identify old age as a perioperative risk factor for cholecystectomy^[17,18]. Thus, it is not clear if laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the best treatment option for elderly patients with ACC nor what the treatment of choice in these patients should be. In contrast, Tokyo Guidelines 2018 for the management of ACC use the ASA-PS classification, CCI together with negative predictive factors of surgical risk in ACC (neurological dysfunction, respiratory dysfunction and coexistence of jaundice) to indicate or not a cholecystectomy^[4]. These latter guides consider as high surgical risk patients with: mild and moderate

cholecystitis (grades I and II) if they present CCI scores ≥ 6 and ASA-PS ≥ 3 , and severe cholecystitis (grade III) if they present CCI scores ≥ 4 and ASA-PS ≥ 3 and negative predictive factors. Both guidelines recommend as a therapeutic alternative the possibility of PC and supportive treatment in patients with a severe and moderate grade of acute cholecystitis when there is a high surgical risk.

There are few studies comparing both techniques and, to date, only one randomized clinical trial, the CHOCOLATE study. Results arising from this recently published study demonstrate the advantages of EC over PC from both clinical and economical considerations^[19].

In our study we have analyzed a large cohort of patients ≥ 70 years and/or ASA-PS ≥ 3 with a diagnosis of ACC undergoing PC or EC over twelve years. To our knowledge, this is the largest study carried out in a single hospital aiming to clarify this issue. In addition, the number of patients to undergo each technique is very similar (222 PC *versus* 239 EC). However, in the high-risk subgroup (≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3), **the number of patients treated by EC was lower**. In this subgroup there were no statistically significant differences in the distribution of comorbidities between the two techniques but the mean age is significantly different (82.42 ± 6.56 years for PC vs. 77.49 ± 5.04 years for EC, $p < 0.001$). This difference suggests the use of age as subjective criteria by surgeons when indicating one treatment or the other^[3]. Some studies seem to show that age is a factor of poor prognosis. *Kirshtein et al*^[17] show in a retrospective cohort study that the age group above and below 75 years has a significant difference in mortality (4.8% versus 0.5%) and morbidity (31% versus 15%)^[17]. Likewise, *Nielsen et al*^[18] reported that the odds ratio for mortality in patients older than 80 years with low risk anaesthetics (ASA-PS ≤ 2) with acute cholecystitis was significantly higher than in age groups of 65 to 79 years and 50 to 64 years (30.9% versus 5.5% versus 1%)^[18]. However, in our study, mortality at 30 and 90 days in patients ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3 undergoing cholecystectomy was

4.62%, lower –but not statistically significant- than in PC. These results suggest that age should not be a factor in deciding the type of treatment.

The most difficult group of patients for deciding on the treatment of ACC are the patients with high surgical risk and advanced age^[20]. *Abi-Haidar et al*^[21] analyzed the results of PC versus EC from 2001 to 2010 and noted that patients with PC were older (70.4 versus 65 years), showed higher ASA-PS grade, had longer hospital stay (20.7 versus 12.1 days), and presented a higher number of complications (2.9 versus 1.9 per patient) and higher rate of readmissions (31.4% versus 13.3%)^[21]. In our study, the results observed in the group of patients ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3 , where PC was most frequently used, were similar to the results published by *Abi-Haidar et al*^[21] for the general population.

The time of evolution of ACC to indicate PC or EC seems not to be relevant in our series. The evolution of ACC was always below the 10 days established in some guidelines as the limit for performing an EC^[3]. Although there were significant differences in the global of patients, these disappear in the high-risk patients subgroup. In addition, in all groups the evolution time between symptom onset and treatment was around 3 days. Time of evolution with ACC greater than or equal to three days was associated with an increased risk of complications and prolongation of hospital stay. As published by *Roulin D et al*^[22] in a randomized study, an EC for ACC even beyond 72 hours of symptoms is safe and associated with less overall morbidity, shorter total hospital stay and reduced cost compared with delayed cholecystectomy^[22].

Melloul et al^[23] published in 2011 a retrospective case control study in critically ill patients with biliary sepsis treated by EC or PC with no differences in mortality rates between the two treatments but with higher complication rate associated with the EC^[23]. In our study, total complications were less frequent in patients undergoing PC but there were no significant differences in the number of severe complications (Clavien-Dindo \geq III). Although there may be a high-risk of

severe complications in the group of patients undergoing PC, this has not reached statistical significance.

Hospital stay, readmissions and mortality at 30 and 90 days was favorable to surgery in all cases. In the group ≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3 mortality does not reach statistical significance but is clearly favorable for the EC group. Mortality rate in this group is similar to that of other published studies (PC 13%, EC 3%) [6,8,21]. In the study by *Lu P et al*^[8] after analyzing 236.742 patients for 10 years PC was associated with a higher rate of mortality and cholecystitis recurrence compared to patients undergoing cholecystectomy even in the worst scenario (elderly patients, CCI of 3 or more)^[8]. In addition, patients treated with a PC in our study, had a significantly greater risk of mortality at 30 and 90 days in all cases.

PC is not a definitive treatment. Although the published resolution rate of ACC is more than 80%, in some cases cholecystectomy is necessary after the acute episode^[6,24]. In our opinion, for patients who underwent PC and cholecystectomy in a second admission, complications, length of hospital stay and mortality derived from this second event should be added to the PC first admission for the definitive comparison of PC and EC. If this were the case, the results of PC could be even worse, as other studies show^[25,26].

As this is a retrospective cohort study, we are aware that there may be some bias in the selection of patients. In order to overcome this limitation, a binary logistic regression analysis was carried out for each of the outcome variables analyzed in order to minimize the effect of the confounding variables.

The conclusions of this study are graphically summarized in Table 4. PC offers less favorable clinical results than EC in the treatment of acute cholecystitis. Mortality at 30 and 90 days, the rate of readmissions and hospital stay offers worse results in the group of patients who underwent PC. Regarding the complication rate, although it is lower in the PC group, severe complications are more frequent (grade III or higher according to the Clavien-Dindo classification). Therefore, PC should not

be considered as an alternative treatment to EC: it should be reserved for patients who refuse to undergo surgery (despite knowing that surgery is the treatment of choice) or when there is an absolute contraindication to perform a cholecystectomy due to very high surgical risk.

REFERENCES

1. Gomes CA, Junior CS, Di Saverio S et al (2017) Acute calculous cholecystitis: Review of current best practices. *World J Gastrointest Surg* 9:118-26. doi: 10.4240/wjgs.v9.i5.118.
2. Kimura Y, Takada T, Kawarada Y et al (2007) Definitions, pathophysiology, and epidemiology of acute cholangitis and cholecystitis: Tokyo Guidelines. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Surg* 14:15-26. doi: 10.1007/s00534-006-1152-y
3. Ansaloni L, Pisano M, Coccolini F et al (2016) 2016 WSES guidelines on acute calculous cholecystitis. *World J Emerg Surg* 11:25. doi: 10.1186/s13017-016-0082-5.
4. Okamoto K, Suzuki K, Takada T et al (2017) Tokyo Guidelines 2018 flowchart for the management of acute cholecystitis. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Sci* doi: 10.1002/jhbp.516.
5. Gurusamy KS, Rossi M, Davidson BR. Percutaneous cholecystostomy for high-risk surgical patients with acute calculous cholecystitis (2013) In: Gurusamy KS, editor. *Cochrane Database Syst. Rev* 8:CD007088.
6. Winbladh A, Gullstrand P, Svanvik J, Sandström P (2009) Systematic review of cholecystostomy as a treatment option in acute cholecystitis. *HPB* 11:183-93. doi: 10.1111/j.1477-2574.2009.00052.x.

7. Sakran N, Kolpelman D, Dar R et al (2018) Outcome of delayed cholecystectomy after percutaneous cholecystostomy for acute cholecystitis. *Isr Med Assoc J* 20:627-631. PMID: 30324780
8. Lu P, Chan C-L, Yang N-P et al (2017) Outcome comparison between percutaneous cholecystostomy and cholecystectomy: a 10-year population-based analysis. *BMC Surg* 17:130. doi: 10.1186/s12893-017-0327-6.
9. Doyle DJ, Garmon EH. American Society of Anesthesiologists Classification (ASA Class). ASA Physical Status Classification System [Updated 2017 Oct 6]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2018. PMID: 28722969
10. Akhan O, Akinci D, Ozman MN (2002) Percutaneous cholecystostomy. *Eur J Radiol* 43:229-36. PMID: 12204405
11. Bakkaloglu H, Yanar H, Guloglu R et al (2006) Ultrasound guided percutaneous cholecystostomy in high-risk patients for surgical intervention. *World J Gastroenterol* 12:7179-82. PMID: 17131483
12. **Strasberg SM, Sanabria JR, Clavien PA (1992) Complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Can J Surg* 35:275-80. PMID:1535545**
13. **Strasberg SM, Hertl M, Soper NJ (1995) An analysis of the problem of biliary injury during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *J Am Coll Surg* 180:101-25. PMID: 8000648**

14. Strasberg SM, Brunt LM (2010) Rationale and use of the critical view of safety laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *J Am Coll Surg* 211:132-38. doi: 10.1016/j.jamcollsurg.2010.02.053

15. Charlson ME, Pompei P, Ales KL, MacKenzie CR (1987) A new method of classifying prognostic comorbidity in longitudinal studies: development and validation. *J Chronic Dis* 40:373-83. PMID: 3558716

16. Dindo D, Demartines N, Clavien P-A (2004) Classification of surgical complications: a new proposal with evaluation in a cohort of 6336 patients and results of a survey. *Ann Surg* 240:205-13. doi: 10.1097/01.sla.0000133083.54934.ae

17. Kirshtein B, Bayme M, Bolotin A et al (2008) Laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis in the elderly: is it safe? *Surg Laparosc Endosc Percutan Tech* 18:334–9. doi: 10.1097/SLE.0b013e318171525d.

18. Nielsen LBJ, Harboe KM, Bardram L (2014) Cholecystectomy for the elderly: no hesitation for otherwise healthy patients. *Surg Endosc* 28:171–7. doi: 10.1007/s00464-013-3144-8.

19. Loozen CS, van Santvoort HC, van Duijvendijk P et al (2018) Laparoscopic cholecystectomy versus percutaneous catheter drainage for acute cholecystitis in high risk patients (CHOCOLATE): multicentre randomised clinical trial. *BMJ* 363:k3965. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k3965>

- 20.** Rodríguez-Sanjuán JC, Arruabarrena A, Sánchez-Moreno L et al (2011) Acute cholecystitis in high surgical risk patients: percutaneous cholecystostomy or emergency cholecystectomy? *Am J Surg* 2012;204:54-9. doi: 10.1016/j.amjsurg.2011.05.013.
- 21.** Abi-Haidar Y, Sanchez V, Williams SA et al (2012) Revisiting Percutaneous Cholecystostomy for Acute Cholecystitis Based on a 10-Year Experience. *Arch Surg* 147:416-22. doi: 10.1001/archsurg.2012.135.
- 22.** Roulin D, Saadi A, Di Mare L et al (2016) Early Versus Delayed Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis, Are the 72 hours Still the Rule?: A Randomized Trial. *Ann Surg* 264: 717-722. doi:10.1097/SLA.0000000000001886
- 23.** Melloul E, Denys A, Demartines N et al (2011) Percutaneous drainage versus emergency cholecystectomy for the treatment of acute cholecystitis in critically ill patients: does it matter? *World J Surg* 35(4):826–33. doi: 10.1007/s00268-011-0985-y.
- 24.** Alvino DML, Fong ZV, McCarthy CJ et al (2017) Long-Term Outcomes Following Percutaneous Cholecystostomy Tube Placement for Treatment of Acute Calculous Cholecystitis. *J Gastrointest Surg* 21:761-9. doi: 10.1007/s11605-017-3375-4.
- 25.** Yuval JB, Mizrahi I, Mazeh H et al (2017) Delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute calculous cholecystitis: is it time for a change? *World J Surg* 41: 1762-68. doi: 10.1007/s00268-017-3928-4.
- 26.** Mizrahi I, Mazeh H, Yuval JB et al (2015) Perioperative outcomes of delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute calculous cholecystitis with and without

percutaneous cholecystostomy. Surgery 158: 728-35. doi:
10.1016/j.surg.2015.05.005.

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FIGURE LEGEND

Figure 1. Distribution of patients according to the inclusion criteria in the study.

Table 1. Demographic profile, comorbidities, complications, hospital stay, readmissions and mortality of the patients included in the study.

Patients (n=461)		PC (n=222)	EC (n=239)	p-value
Age (mean ± SD)		78.63 ± 10.91	74.06 ± 9.36	<0.001
Gender	Men	115	138	0.2
	Women	107	101	
Time of evolution^a (mean ± SD)		3.65 (±3.5)	2.50(±2.09)	<0.001
Comorbidities	Diabetes Mellitus	94	80	0.054
	Arterial Hypertension	144	139	0.127
	Heart disease	72	46	0.001
ASA-PS^b	I/II	54	127	0.001
	III/IV	165	112	0.001
CCI^c	<6	215	237	0.073
	≥6	7	2	0.073
Complications^d	Total	31 (14%)	54 (22.6%)	0.017
	I-II	16	43	
	III-V	15	11	
Hospital stay in days (mean ± SD)		13.21 ± 8.18	7.48 ± 7.67	<0,001
Readmissions	Total	78 (35.1%)	30 (12.6%)	<0,001
	Biliary pathology ^e	65	16	
	Technique complications	8	12	
	Others	5	2	
Mortality	30 days	19 (8.6%)	4 (1.7%)	0.001
	90 days	23 (10.4%)	5 (2.1%)	<0.001

^aTime from the appearance of the first symptoms until the patient consults in the hospital.

^bContrast hypothesis between type of intervention and score ASA-PS 1-2 versus ASA-PS 3-4.

^cContrast hypothesis between type of intervention and CCI ≥6 versus CCI <6.

^dComplications according to the Clavien-Dindo classification.

^eBiliary pathology includes: acute cholecystitis, cholangitis, choledocholithiasis and acute pancreatitis.

Table 2. Demographic profile, comorbidities, complications, hospital stay, readmissions and mortality of the high-risk subgroup of patients (≥ 70 years plus ASA-PS ≥ 3).

Patients ≥ 70 years and ASA-PS ≥ 3		PC (n=128)	EC (n=65)	p-value
Age (mean \pm SD)		82.42 (\pm 6.56)	77.49 (\pm 5.04)	<0.001
Gender	Men	63	45	0.008
	Women	65	20	
Time of evolution^a (media \pm DE)		3.49 (\pm 3.45)	2.73 (\pm 2.54)	0.092
Comorbidities	Diabetes Mellitus	63	27	0.312
	Arterial Hypertension	91	39	0.120
	Heart disease	63	28	0.419
CCI^b	<6	160	110	0.498
	≥ 6	5	2	0.498
Complications^c	Total	18 (14%)	27 (41.5%)	0.036
	I-II	7	21	
	III-V	11	6	
Hospital stay in days (mean \pm SD)		12.95 \pm 7.25	11.23 \pm 11.6	<0.001
Readmission	Total	44 (34.3%)	7 (10.7%)	<0.001
	Biliary pathology ^d	35	4	
	Technique Complications	5	3	
	Others	4	0	
Mortality	30 days	13 (10.16%)	3 (4.62%)	0.189
	90 days	17 (13.28%)	3 (4.62%)	0.062

^aTime from the appearance of the first symptoms until the patient consults in the hospital.

^bContrast hypothesis between type of intervention and ≥ 6 versus CCI <6.

^cComplications according to the Clavien-Dindo classification

^dBiliary pathology includes: acute cholecystitis, cholangitis, choledocholithiasis and acute pancreatitis.

Table 3. Binary logistic regression analysis for the outcome variables.

	Total		≥70 years + ASA-PS ≥3	
	OR (CI 95%)	p	OR (CI 95%)	p
INTERVENTION (PC)				
Gender (OR:men)	0.678 (0.449-1.024)	0.064	0.643 (0.414-0.999)	0.050
Age (OR≥70years)	2.450 (1.401-4.283)	0.002	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	4.749 (2.838-7.949)	<0.001	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	1.112 (0.720-1.716)	0.633	1.227 (0.772-1.950)	0.387
Arterial Hypertension (OR: yes)	1.149 (0.750-1.763)	0.523	1.401 (0.884-2.220)	0.151
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	0.980 (0.582-1.650)	0.939	2.922 (1.731-4.932)	<0.001
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	3.643 (2.313-5.737)	<0.001	3.633 (2.224-5.935)	<0.001
COMPLICATIONS				
Intervention (OR:PC)	0.408 (0.237-0.703)	0.001	0.374 (0.201-0.696)	0.002
Gender (OR:men)	1.169 (0.712-1.921)	0.538	1.164 (0.632-2.144)	0.626
Age (OR≥70years)	1.690 (0.861-3.317)	0.127	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	2.609 (1.362-4.998)	0.016	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	0.880 (0.521-1.487)	0.634	0.962 (0.522-1.772)	0.900
Arterial Hypertension (OR: yes)	0.628 (0.381-1.036)	0.068	0.768 (0.415-1.423)	0.402
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	1.500 (0.840-2.679)	0.116	1.518 (0.838-2.749)	0.168
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	1.582 (0.927-2.701)	0.093	2.653 (1.415-4.975)	0.002
SEVERE COMPLICATIONS				
Intervention (OR:PC)	1.054 (0.447-2.482)	0.905	1.230 (0.461-3.288)	0.509
Gender (OR:men)	0.906 (0.411-1.994)	0.806	0.929 (0.386-2.236)	0.869
Age (OR≥70years)	2.254 (0.708-7.178)	0.169	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	3.987 (1.279-12.425)	0.017	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	0.691 (0.298-1.601)	0.388	0.785 (0.320-1.926)	0.596
Arterial Hypertension (OR: yes)	0.682 (0.307-1.518)	0.349	0.904 (0.364-2.249)	0.829
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	1.286 (0.541-3.056)	0.570	1.447 (0.610-3.432)	0.402
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	2.265 (1.017-5.045)	0.045	2.715 (1.133-6.509)	0.025
HOSPITAL STAY				
Intervention (OR:PC)	8.708 (5.346-14.184)	<0.001	7.446 (3.980-13.928)	<0.001
Gender (OR:men)	1.211 (0.768-1.909)	0.411	1.171 (0.651-2.106)	0.598
Age (OR≥70years)	2.346 (1.236-4.452)	0.009	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	1.784 (1.005-3.166)	0.048	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	1.298 (0.802-2.102)	0.288	2.108 (1.158-3.836)	0.015
Arterial Hypertension (OR: yes)	0.802 (0.500-1.287)	0.361	0.667 (0.362-1.231)	0.195
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	0.864 (0.477-1.565)	0.630	0.862 (0.480-1.548)	0.619
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	2.026 (1.210-3.395)	0.007	1.320 (0.688-2.532)	0.403
Complications (OR:yes)	2.620 (1.456-4.714)	0.001	3.073 (1.474-6.408)	0.003

READMISSION				
Intervention (OR:PC)	4.685 (2.602-8.434)	<0.001	8.935 (2.241-10.868)	<0.001
Gender (OR:men)	0.992 (0.623-1.580)	0.975	1.003 (0.552-1.823)	0.991
Age (OR≥70years)	1.279 (0.641-2.552)	0.485	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	0.972 (0.538-1.755)	0.924	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	0.888 (0.540-1.462)	0.641	0.625 (0.337-1.162)	0.137
Arterial Hypertension (OR: yes)	0.753 (0.464-1.223)	0.251	1.044 (0.556-1.963)	0.893
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	0.533 (0.290-0.980)	0.043	0.512 (0.275-0.953)	0.035
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	0.931 (0.563-1.539)	0.780	1.027 (0.545-1.933)	0.935
Hospital Stay (OR:≥7days)	1.039 (0.600-1.797)	0.892	1.498 (0.731-3.071)	0.269
Complications (OR: yes)	2.154 (1.213-3.824)	0.009	1.610 (0.782-3.313)	0.196
30 DAYS MORTALITY				
Intervention (OR:PC)	18.397 (4.270-79.263)	<0.001	22.102 (3.276-149.126)	0.001
Gender (OR:men)	0.335 (0.104-1.076)	0.66	0.166 (0.031-0.886)	0.036
Age (OR≥70years)	5.210 (0.637-42.600)	0.124	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	1.396 (0.296-6.578)	0.673	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	0.480 (0.135-1.707)	0.257	0.266 (0.051-1.392)	0.117
Arterial Hypertension (OR:yes)	0.847 (0.268-2.678)	0.847	0.975 (0.208-4.564)	0.974
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	1.320 (0.348-5.014)	0.683	1.942 (0.456-8.266)	0.369
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	1.496 (0.481-4.654)	0.487	0.888 (0.181-4.348)	0.883
Complications (OR: yes)	37.109 (10.707-128.6115)	<0.001	99.957 (14.991-666.483)	<0.001
Hospital Stay (OR≥7 days)	0.291 (0.089-0.955)	0.042	0.225 (0.048-1.048)	0.057
Readmission (OR:yes)	0.055 (0.006-0.487)	0.009	---	0.996
90 DAYS MORTALITY				
Intervention (OR:PC)	10.261 (2.936-35.857)	<0.001	10.762 (2.348-49.334)	0.002
Gender (OR:men)	0.281 (0.102-0.772)	0.014	0.210 (0.062-0.715)	0.013
Age (OR≥70years)	7.776 (1.149-52.606)	0.035	---	---
ASA-PS (OR≥III)	2.085 (0.592-7.393)	0.253	---	---
Diabetes Mellitus (OR: yes)	0.423 (0.142-1.258)	0.122	0.319 (0.090-1.135)	0.078
Arterial Hypertension (OR:yes)	0.906 (0.335-2.453)	0.846	1.271 (0.307-4.364)	0.703
Heart Disease (OR: yes)	0.950 (0.312-2.896)	0.683	1.448 (0.471-4.453)	0.518
Time of evolution (OR≥3days)	2.439 (0.931-6.393)	0.070	2.437 (0.762-7.790)	0.133
Complications (OR: yes)	20.211 (7.082-57.681)	<0.001	19.427 (5.533-68.212)	<0.001
Hospital Stay (OR≥7 days)	0.501 (0.179-1.405)	0.189	0.446 (0.133-1.492)	0.190
Readmission (OR:yes)	0.260 (0.073-0.927)	0.038	0.110 (0.19-0.653)	0.015

Table 4. Graphic summary of the results according to the treatment used.

	Complications	Severe Complications ^b	Hospital stay	Readmissions	Mortality 30 days	Mortality 90 days
Percutaneous cholecystostomy (PC)	+					
Emergency cholecystectomy (EC)		+	+	+	+	+
^a The result in favour of the procedure is marked with + ^b Clavien-Dindo classification \geq III						